

The D⁴ Advantage in Practice: Comparing Near-Infrared Sensitivity of TMT, ELT, and GMT

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ABSTRACT

The coming decade will see the operation of three Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs)—the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT), the European Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), and the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT)—each designed to deliver diffraction-limited imaging and spectroscopy across the near-infrared (NIR) regime. These facilities will open new discovery space in exoplanet characterization, stellar populations, and galaxy formation through both their unprecedented angular resolution and sensitivities far beyond current 8-10 m class telescopes. However, realizing these gains in practice requires more than large apertures. The achieved sensitivity depends on a combination of collecting area, adaptive optics performance, optical throughput, and the thermal and sky background seen by the instrument. This study quantifies the point-source sensitivity achievable by each facility in the background-limited, diffraction-limited regime under realistic assumptions, highlighting the physical origin of the “D⁴ advantage” and the instrumental factors that determine the relative sensitivity performance of the ELTs.

Keywords: Extremely Large Telescopes; TMT; E-ELT; GMT; near-infrared sensitivity

1. INTRODUCTION

The coming decade will mark the transition of ground-based astronomy into a new era with the commissioning of the three Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs): the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT), the European Extremely Large Telescope (E-ELT), and the Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT). With primary mirror diameters of 25-39 meters, these facilities promise a transformative increase in both angular resolution and sensitivity relative to current 8-10 m observatories. In the near-infrared (NIR), where adaptive optics (AO) correction is most effective, ELTs are expected to routinely deliver images approaching the diffraction limit, enabling studies of faint exoplanets, resolved stellar populations in nearby galaxies, and the dynamics of galactic nuclei at unprecedented precision.

A central motivation for these facilities is the so-called D⁴ advantage. For background-limited, diffraction-limited point-source observations, the exposure time required to reach a given S/N scales inversely as the collecting area ($\propto D^2$) and benefits from an additional factor of D² due to the concentration of light into a diffraction core whose area shrinks as $(\lambda/D)^2$. However, achieving this D⁴ advantage in practice requires not only larger apertures but also high Strehl ratios, efficient optical throughput, low thermal emissivity, and careful control of background and operational overheads. In this paper, we quantify the near-infrared point-source sensitivity achievable by TMT, E-ELT, and GMT under realistic assumptions, isolating the physical and instrumental factors that determine how closely each facility approaches the theoretical D⁴ regime.

While the focus of this paper is the comparison among the three ELTs, it is important to emphasize that all three facilities represent a dramatic advance relative to the current generation of 8-10 m telescopes such as Keck, the Very Large Telescope (VLT), and Gemini. The D⁴ advantage implies that moving from a 10 m telescope to a 30-40 m class facility will result in potential gains approaching two orders of magnitude in observing efficiency. Programs that

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currently require tens of nights on existing facilities can, in principle, be completed in a few hours on an ELT. Equally important, the improvement in angular resolution, from roughly 40-50 mas in the near-infrared to 10-15 mas, opens entirely new regimes of astrophysical investigation, including direct spectroscopy of faint exoplanets, resolved stellar populations in galaxies beyond the Local Group, and precision astrometry in crowded environments such as the Galactic Center. In this sense, the comparison among ELTs discussed below should be viewed within the broader context of a transformative step forward for ground-based astronomy.

2. A COMPARATIVE EXPOSURE TIME CALCULATOR

The D^4 advantage is best understood as an upper bound on what diffraction-limited ELTs can deliver, not as an automatic outcome of aperture alone. In practice, the exposure-time scaling for background-limited point sources includes multiplicative “efficiency terms” that can easily erode the idealized gain: imperfect AO correction broadens the effective point source function (PSF) core, throughput losses reduce detected signal, pupil geometry changes how much energy falls inside a practical extraction aperture, and thermal emissivity and sky background set the background floor (particularly in K-band). Including these factors, we can find that the exposure time, t_{exp} , scales as $t_{\text{exp}} \propto b / (A_{\text{tel}} \times D^2 \times \epsilon \times \text{Strehl}^2 \times \eta_{\text{diff}}^2)$ where b is the background level, A_{tel} is the telescope collecting area, D is the telescope diameter, ϵ is the total system throughput (including optical throughput and detector quantum efficiency), and η_{diff} is the fraction of light from the perfect diffraction-limited PSF contained within an extraction aperture of diameter $1.5 \lambda/D$.

The goal of our comparative exposure time calculator (ETC) is therefore not to reproduce full facility-specific ETCs, but to isolate and quantify the leading-order physical terms that determine the point source sensitivity of the three ELTs. The ETC includes additional inputs to calculate either Signal-to-Noise (S/N) for a given exposure time and point source brightness, or exposure time for a given S/N and brightness, but Table 1 shows the main elements of the scaling relation and are discussed in more detail below.

Table 1. Comparison of key ELT point source sensitivity factors

Parameter	E-ELT	TMT	GMT
A_{tel} – Collecting Area	980 m ²	634 m ²	356 m ²
D – Diameter	39 m	30 m	25.4 m
ϵ (end-to-end throughput)	37%	41%	43%
LGS Strehl (H-band)	37%	47%	40%
η_{diff} (Light within diffraction core)	63%	68%	56%
$t_{\text{exp}} / t_{\text{exp}} (\text{E-ELT})$	1	1.2	6.0

In addition to the importance of the telescope diameter and collecting area, optical throughput helps drive sensitivity. In the comparative ETC we treat throughput as the product of several terms: atmospheric transmission (evaluated at 30° from zenith and equal for the three ELT sites), telescope throughput derived from published coating curves and the number of reflections (Figure 1), AO system throughput, instrument throughput, and detector quantum efficiency. The AO throughput assumptions differ slightly among facilities. For TMT NFIRAOS [3] and E-ELT MORFEO [2], the AO relay introduces several additional reflections that are included in the throughput model, whereas for GMT we assume only minimal loss associated with a dichroic beamsplitter because the adaptive secondary mirrors provide AO correction without a separate relay. To isolate telescope and AO effects, we assume identical post-AO imagers for all facilities, adopting a throughput of 60% and a detector quantum efficiency of 85% in the J, H, and K bands. These assumptions provide an intentionally level playing field, since individual instruments will ultimately differ in their optical designs and efficiencies. Even under these controlled assumptions, modest differences in total throughput (roughly 6% across ELTs) translate directly into comparable differences in required exposure time and can become amplified when combined with background terms.

Figure 1. Comparison of the optical design of the European ELT (We use E-ELT in this paper to avoid confusion with the class of Extremely Large Telescopes) and TMT. The E-ELT has five reflections before reaching the Nasmyth platform and includes a sixth mirror that folds the light into MORFEO. TMT has three reflective surfaces before the light enters NFIRAOS.

A term related but distinct from the system throughput is derived from the pupil geometry and diffraction structure. Even for systems that share identical Strehl ratios and diameters, different obscurations and segmentation patterns redistribute energy between the diffraction core and halo. This matters because the ETC optimizes signal-to-noise in a finite extraction aperture (here tied to $\sim 1.5 \lambda/D$), so what matters is not only the Strehl but also the fraction of the perfect diffraction-limited PSF enclosed by the chosen aperture (η_{diff}). The filled-aperture character and relatively small obscuration of TMT concentrate more energy into the core and produce a smoother diffraction pattern, which results in a higher core coupling and less pronounced diffraction patterns (Figure 2). GMT, with its seven separate primary mirrors with significant gaps leads to a number of diffraction features in the PSF. E-ELT has a filled aperture, but a very large central obscuration so η_{diff} for E-ELT falls between that of TMT and GMT. The ETC captures this effect by explicitly including an encircled-energy term for the perfect PSF, separate from Strehl losses.

An important term in our point source sensitivity calculation is the AO residual wavefront error (WFE), which enters primarily through the Strehl ratio (Figure 2). For diffraction-limited point sources extracted over an aperture scaled to λ/D , the exposure time depends steeply on Strehl because the fraction of source photons concentrated into the diffraction core scales with Strehl. In the simplified background-limited formulation used here, t_{exp} scales approximately as $1/\text{Strehl}^2$ (with additional dependence through the diffraction-encircled-energy term), so modest Strehl differences translate into large changes in observing efficiency. Strehl is therefore a key first-order modifier of the idealized D^4 scaling, alongside throughput and background, and AO architecture becomes an important differentiator between facilities especially in J and H-bands.

For the ETC we created we assume median atmospheric conditions and a zenith angle of 30 degrees. Under these conditions, we adopted the NFIRAOS WFE requirement in Laser Guide Star (LGS) Multi-Conjugate AO (MCAO) mode of 225 nm RMS. This corresponds to a Strehl ratio of 47% in H-band [7][8]. In the narrow-field Natural Guide Star (NGS) AO mode, the WFE is 165 nm RMS [7]. Both these values have been calculated for the Observatorio del Roque de los Muchachos site. For MORFEO, the LGS MCAO WFE over a 20 arcsecond diameter field is 260 nm RMS [4] as reported by the MORFEO team corresponding to a H-band Strehl of 37%. In narrow-band NGS mode, MORFEO is expected to deliver a WFE of 210 nm RMS. The difference in WFE budgets between TMT NFIRAOS and E-ELT MORFEO are due to the larger expected wind shake experienced by E-ELT, and the larger isoplanatic angle at ORM compared to Cerro Armazones, Chile [5], which benefits tomographic correction at the TMT site. Finally, we assign a WFE of 250 nm RMS to GMT Laser Tomography AO (LTAO) mode, which is slightly better than the reported 280 nm RMS current best estimate of WFE [1]. The value we used corresponds to a 40% H-band Strehl. In NGS mode, the WFE mode for GMT is 157 nm RMS (corresponding to the current best estimate [1]). We use the Maréchal approximation to estimate the Strehl ratio in different bands.

We also include the effect of the thermal background in K-band, where thermal emission from the telescope and AO relay can dominate over sky background. The ETC therefore treats emissivity as an input: warm optics increase the photon background, and AO system temperature matters directly. Based on site testing data, the median temperature at TMT’s ORM site is 7.5 degrees, virtually the same as E-ELT’s Cerro Armazones site [5]. GMT’s Las Campanas site is slightly warmer, with a median nighttime temperature of 11 degrees [6]. We assume all imagers include a cold stop when observing in K-band. TMT decided to prioritize K-band imaging and spectroscopy, which drove the NFIRAOS design to cool the AO relay to -30°C to reduce thermal emission. The E-ELT MORFEO system operates at ambient temperatures. GMT, because the AO correction is provided solely by the adaptive secondary mirrors, suffers less from thermal emission because no AO relay is required. The decision whether to cool the AO system can be the difference between “diameter-dominated” expectations and realized sensitivity at longer NIR wavelengths. While the ETC used in this comparison does not include a full sky model, it does compare facilities under consistent assumptions of sky plus thermal backgrounds and highlights when background limits sensitivity.

Figure 2. The filled pupil of TMT concentrates somewhat more energy into the diffraction core, which can improve coupling efficiency for point-source extraction. TMT NFIRAOS also achieves a higher MCAO Strehl ratio than E-ELT MORFEO because: MORFEO has been optimized for a bigger field (wider LGS separation); E-ELT expects to have more windshake and vibration. GMT AO uses laser tomography AO in place of MCAO and also expects lower Strehl ratios. See text for references.

The ETC is constructed to be deliberately “controlled”: we assume an identical post-AO imager (detector format/QE/readnoise/filter model) so that differences in sensitivity are driven by telescope + AO + background terms rather than downstream instrument implementation. Specifically, the parameters held constant across all three facilities are: atmospheric transmission (evaluated at 30° zenith), sky background model, extraction aperture diameter ($1.5 \lambda/D$), instrument throughput (60%), and detector quantum efficiency (85%). The parameters that vary by facility are: primary mirror diameter, collecting area (accounting for central obstructions), number of warm reflections, AO relay emissivity and temperature, and AO system WFE. The ETC can either calculate S/N in a given time or exposure time to reach a S/N for a given stellar magnitude for a generic imager. The calculator computes (1) source counts delivered into the extraction aperture after throughput, Strehl, and diffraction encircled-energy factors; (2) background counts from sky plus thermal emission using emissivity and site temperature assumptions; and (3) total noise including read noise where relevant. We then validate the calculator by cross-checking representative configurations against facility ETCs (e.g., IRIS¹, GMTIFS²)

¹ <https://www.tmt.org/etc/iris>

² <https://www.mso.anu.edu.au/gmtifs/Performance/GMTIFS-Imager-ETC.html>

to ensure the simplified model reproduces the correct order-of-magnitude behavior and the expected band-to-band transitions between source-limited and background-limited regimes. We found agreement between ETCs during testing on the level of 10-15% in predicted exposure time for a given S/N.

3. RESULTS

Using the framework described above, we computed the exposure time required to reach specified signal-to-noise ratios for diffraction-limited imaging in the J, H, and K bands. The results presented here are strictly for imaging with an idealized post-AO imager, but they are highly suggestive of the performance that diffraction-limited imagers and integral-field spectrographs will achieve in practice, since the dominant sensitivity terms—collecting area, Strehl ratio, diffraction-core concentration, throughput, and thermal background—enter identically for point-source extraction in narrow spatial apertures. The plots that follow show relative exposure times and corresponding limiting magnitudes for TMT, E-ELT, and GMT under consistent assumptions, allowing direct comparison of realized sensitivity rather than idealized D^4 expectations.

Across all bands, the limiting magnitude comparison reflects the interplay between aperture, AO correction, and background. In J and H bands, where thermal emission is modest and the sky background is dominated by OH emission, collecting area and Strehl ratio are the primary drivers. In these regimes, E-ELT’s larger diameter offsets part of the sensitivity differences associated with AO performance, leading to broadly comparable limiting magnitudes between TMT and E-ELT for on-axis observations (Figure 3). In K band, however, thermal background becomes increasingly important. Here, the reduced emissivity associated with fewer warm reflections and a cooled AO relay shifts the balance, and TMT’s background control offsets the larger collecting area of E-ELT, resulting in comparable, or in some cases shorter, exposure times for equivalent signal-to-noise.

Figure 3. Limiting H-band (left) and K-band (right) magnitudes as a function of exposure time in seconds for S/N=50 for the premier current or planned international observatories. TMT and E-ELT offer comparable near-infrared sensitivity, surpassing any other present or planned ground-based telescope. In the K-band, TMT performance exceeds E-ELT because the telescope has fewer reflections and the TMT NFIRAOS AO system is cooled to -30°C .

These trends make clear that diameter alone does not set performance. When AO correction is strong and thermal backgrounds are controlled, TMT and E-ELT achieve broadly comparable near-infrared sensitivity, with differences depending on wavelength band and observing mode. In scenarios where Strehl ratio differences are significant, particularly in MCAO modes over finite fields, the sensitivity scaling with Strehl^2 becomes an important factor. Small differences in residual wavefront error propagate into measurable differences in limiting magnitude, especially in background-limited regimes. The ETC results therefore reinforce a central conclusion: sensitivity trends track Strehl and emissivity in addition to collecting area.

To illustrate these general results in concrete terms, we constructed three representative case studies. The first case study probes the source-limited regime at peak on-axis AO performance. It considers a high signal-to-noise point-source program, requiring $S/N \geq 500$ for a target with J, H, and K AB magnitudes of 24. In this case, we assume the AO systems are all operating in their best on-axis case corresponding to NGS AO with a bright star although such faint targets would not themselves serve as natural guide stars, but nevertheless we make the assumption that each ELT AO system is operating at peak performance. This is clearly a best-case scenario, and it favors the E-ELT and GMT as the resultant AO correction

across all three telescopes are more uniform. This source-limited scenario approximates a deep spectroscopic follow-up with a $S/N \approx 5$ in the continuum at a resolution of 4000. Note that the different spectrographs on ELTs all have significant differences driven by their science cases, so we did not attempt to build a common spectroscopic ETC. For this source-limited case, exposure times for TMT and E-ELT are similar in J and H-bands, with differences tracking Strehl assumptions. In K, thermal background shifts the advantage toward the lower-emissivity configuration. GMT, operating primarily in LTAO mode, demonstrates strong on-axis performance but exposure times are longer due to its smaller collecting area and lower fraction of light in the diffraction-limited core due to the telescope geometry (η_{diff}). Figure 4 shows the number of such programs that could be completed per night using the ELTs. To calculate the program time, we include overheads associated with acquisition, readouts, and dithers (assuming the target can be dithered on the integral field unit). These overheads amount to $\sim 20\%$ of the exposure time with only a small variation among telescopes.

Figure 4. Comparison of ETC results for three programs in J, H, and K-bands: a brighter target at high S/N corresponding to a spectroscopic observations (left), a single MCAO field survey observing fainter targets at moderate S/N (center), and then an imaging program requiring a larger field at the same depth that takes advantage of E-ELT MORFEO’s wide field mode (right).

The second case study probes the background-limited MCAO survey regime. It considers an AO imaging program over a 20×20 square arcsecond field of view where the intent is to reach a S/N of 50 down to an AB magnitude of 26 (Figure 4). This field of view for this program was chosen to match the narrow field delivered by E-ELT MORFEO. TMT NFIRAOS+IRIS covers 34×34 square arcseconds. In this case, the MCAO architecture of MORFEO and NFIRAOS plays an important role. We expect that these MCAO systems can both cover the 20×20 square arcsecond field with a single pointing. GMT operates in LTAO mode, so the effective field of view will be limited by the isoplanatic angle (Figure 5). GMT LTAO would therefore have to use at least 4 separate pointings to cover the same field. Because exposure time depends not only on on-axis Strehl but also on uniformity across the science field, differences in corrected field size and tomographic error influence survey efficiency. In the comparison of the number of programs per night that can be performed, we have included all overheads as discussed above. The ETC results show that for fields comparable to the NFIRAOS science field, TMT can achieve shorter integration times than E-ELT in K band and comparable times in J and H, even though E-ELT has the larger aperture.

The third case study probes wide-field survey efficiency and the MCAO field-of-view advantage. It considers an AO imaging program over a 100 x 100 square arcsecond field of view with a S/N of 50 for stars with AB magnitudes of 26. This field of view for this program was chosen to match the 50 arcsecond wide field delivered by E-ELT MORFEO so MORFEO requires 4 pointings to cover the field. TMT NFIRAOS+IRIS covers 34 x 34 square arcseconds, so it takes 9 pointings to cover this field. GMT in LTAO mode would require at least 36 separate pointings to cover this wide field.

Figure 5. TMT NFIRAOS is a Multi-Conjugate Adaptive Optics (MCAO) System. NFIRAOS provides a high performance, uniform correction over a 1 arcminute diameter field of view. MCAO also helps sharpen guide stars to improve sky coverage. LTAO systems provide a wider corrected field than SCAO but do not match the large, uniform field of MCAO.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The comparative ETC analysis highlights that the realized sensitivity of ELTs depends on several coupled factors, but their relative importance is not equal. For diffraction-limited, background-limited observations, the dominant drivers of sensitivity are (1) the telescope collecting area and diffraction-limited image size, (2) AO performance, expressed primarily through the Strehl ratio, (3) the energy concentration in the diffraction-limited PSF core, (4) optical throughput, determined by the number of reflections and coating efficiencies, and the (5) thermal background and emissivity, particularly in K-band. Because exposure time scales roughly as $1/\text{Strehl}^2$ in the simplified regime considered here, even modest differences in AO performance can rival the gains expected from larger apertures.

This scaling provides a useful rule of thumb for interpreting the results. The difference between a 30 m and 39 m aperture corresponds to roughly a factor of $(39/30)^2 \approx 1.7$ in collecting area and $(39/30)^4 \approx 2.9$ in the idealized D^4 regime. However, in the background-limited diffraction-limited regime represented in the ETC, a difference in Strehl ratio of order 15–20% can produce a comparable change in exposure time (for example, a facility with a Strehl of 50% versus 30% gains a factor of ~ 2.8 in observing efficiency from Strehl alone). In other words, a facility delivering significantly higher Strehl can offset a substantial fraction of the sensitivity advantage implied by several meters of additional aperture. This sensitivity to Strehl also means that the results depend on assumptions about residual wavefront error, thermal emissivity, and sky background.

Taken together, these results reinforce an important point about the role of the D^4 advantage. The D^4 scaling provides a benchmark for the ultimate potential of diffraction-limited ELTs, but it is not guaranteed in practice. Achieving sensitivities close to this limit requires careful optimization across the entire observatory system, including telescope optical design, AO architecture, thermal environment, and operational efficiency. Among these factors, adaptive optics performance is one of several first-order sensitivity drivers, alongside collecting area, throughput, and thermal background,

because it directly controls how effectively light is concentrated into the diffraction-limited core. The results therefore suggest a broader design philosophy for ELTs: while aperture establishes the fundamental discovery space, the ability to approach the D^4 regime ultimately depends on how well the observatory delivers stable, high-Strehl diffraction-limited images with minimal background and high throughput.

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